

MOLECULAR TAXONOMIC STUDY FOR THE GENUS *JUNCUS* L. (JUNCACEAE) IN IRAQ BASED ON CHLOROPLAST GENE RPL16.

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Abstract

This study examines the taxonomic significance of the intron chloroplast gene *rpl16* in molecular research (Phylogenetic Relationships) between *Juncus* (Juncaceae) family in Iraq comprising diagnostic molecular study obtained from sequencing of *rpl16* gene. The study showed cluster analysis and distributed the *Juncus* species in three major clades, and the basal clade included *J. articulatus* alone; this clade sister clade to the second major clade, the *J. maritimus* & *J. acutatus* clade. The third clade in the phylogenetic tree gathers the *J. hybridus* & *J. rigidus*. Monophyly of these clades good in supported and relationship between *Juncus* species in Iraq clear based on molecular data.

Keywords: Molecular , *Juncus* L., Juncaceae , chloroplast gene RPL16.

Introduction

Juncaceae family with 6 genera and some 345 species throughout the world (Singh, 2010). In Iraq has 12 species dispersed on only 1 genus (Al-Rawi, 1964) while in the flora of Iraq to Townsend and Guest the genera *Juncus* has 16 species. but Rechinger (1964) indicated 6 species of the genus *Juncus* in the low lands of Iraq .furthermore, Snogerup (1985b) declared 16 species , Ridda and Daood (1982) mentioned 14 species, Khalaf, (1980) mentioned 1 species in Sinjar mountain. Faris (1983), Fatah (2003)and Ahmed (2010), record 2 species in PiraMagrun, Haibat Sultan and Gomaspan mountains respectively, Ahmad (2013) mentioned 3 species in Hawraman mountain. but Darwesh (2017) and Hameed (2016) didn't mention any species in Choman and Hujran respectively . Rechinger (1971) referred to that 28 species of the genus *Juncus* existing In Iran, whereas Ghahreman and Attar (1999) indicated 20 species. In Turkey and Snogerup (1985a) specified 34 species of the genus *Juncus*., ,

Two genera of Juncaceae, *Oxychloë* and *Prionium*, are not closely related to the other genera of this family. Furthermore , Cyperaceae was more closely related to Juncaceae than to Poaceae. So, Cyperaceae appear to be derived from within Juncaceae. (Gregory, et. al., 1995).

A jackknife analysis revealed several well-supported clades. *Luzula* is monophyletic and *Juncus* is non-monophyletic. (Záveská, et. al., 2003).

Chromosome patterns are complex, given the levels of aneuploidy/polyploidy in the Juncaceae family, but there appears to be a split between the *Juncus*-dominated clades, with diploid chromosome numbers generally in multiples of 10 or 20 and apparent aneuploid derivatives, and the *Luzula* clade with diploid chromosome numbers generally in multiples of 6 or 12. (Roalson, 2005).

The statistical parsimony network approach showed that ribotypes ancient and haplotypes co-occur with their descendants in *Luzula*. In *Luzula* section *Luzula*, both recent hybridisation and incomplete lineage sorting of ancestral polymorphisms may represent potential sources of the incongruence between chloroplast and nuclear data. (Záveská, et. al., 2010).

The objective of this study were to use the DNA sequences information from the Chloroplast RPL16 gene for *Juncus* species in Iraq to reconstruct a phylogenetic tree and use it for the assessment of species relationships.

Materials and Methods

Species sampling

"The RPL16 gene were sequenced from 5 accessions representing 5 species of *Juncus*. The RPL16 gene were chose based on their documented utility in phylogenetics. Accessions for a species with identical DNA sequences were represented by one accession in dataset to speed up Phylogenetic analysis."

DNA Isolation, Amplification, and sequencing.

"For fresh material, genomic DNA was isolated following Doyle & Doyle (1990). In the case of herbarium sample (more than 40 years old), the DNA isolation method was modified to optimize the procedure. In those cases, the leaf material was extracted two to three times in CTAB+ Beta-mercaptoethanol and the supernatant solutions collected from each extraction were combined to increase the amount of DNA recovered. Additionally, the solution was allowed to remain at -20 °

C overnight at the DNA precipitation step. The RPL16 gene was amplified using the universal primers RPL16 and the protocol from Taberlet et al., (1991) with a 50 °C annealing Temperature and the polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) method described in Wood et al., (2005). Amplification products for RPL16 gene were resolved on 0.8% TAE-agarose gels, excised, and cleaned QIA quick PCR purification. Cycle sequencing was performed using performed using the ABI PRISM Big Dye terminator Cycle Sequencing Kit v.3.1 (Applied Biosystem, Foster City, California, USA) and the products were resolved using Applied Biosystem 3730 automated sequencer at the Core Sequencing Facility at the DNA Analysis Facility of Duke University".

Outgroup selection.

Luzula acuminata were selected as outgroup in the RPL16 phylogenetic analysis according to traditional and current systematic studies and the flora of Iraq Vol.5, P.2. That demonstrated the species of the genus are closely related to each other.

Sequences alignment and phylogenetic construction.

"The RPL16 sequences were aligned automatically using Quicalign v.1.03 (Muller ,2004). The data set were analyzed using maximum parsimony (MP) & Maximum Likelihood (ML) in PAUP* (Sofford,2002). In the MP analysis, heuristic search were performed with all characters equally weighted. A strict consensus tree was computed from all shortest trees. Maximum Likelihood bootstrap values as a measure of clade support (Felsenstein , 1985) were obtained by conducting

searches of 1000 iterations with 10 random sequence replicates. our partitioned analyses demonstrated the differences between the topologies of the trees derived from the Maximum Parsimony and Maximum Likelihood analysis".

Results & Discussion.

The RPL16 gene varied in length from 2012 bp in (*Juncus rigidus*) to 2430 bp in (*juncus maritimus*) nucleotides which is the first good character in separation of species under studies. After the insertions of 14 gaps of 1 to 4 bp in length, the alignment was 2430 characters long. In the ends of the alignment, we exclusion portions due to missing data.

The topologies obtained from the Maximum parsimony and maximum Likelihood analysis are completely congruent and the phylogenetic tree discussed to gather.

The cladogram of *Juncus* received good BS support (Fig.1). A split into two major clades is evident at the base of the genus. the first clade (75%) comprises *Juncus articulatus* alone and the second clade divided in to two secondary clade, *Juncus maritimus* sister *Juncus actus* and the second secondary clade representing *Juncus hybridus* sister *Juncus rigidus* with medium (69% BS) (Fig.1).

In Maximum Likelihood analysis the monophyly of *Juncus* is supported by maximum PP and 100% BS (Fig.2). (*Juncus rigidus* and *Juncus hybridus*) emerge as consecutive sisters to *Juncus maritimus* & *Juncus actus* and *Juncus articulatus* with full bootstrapping value 100%. (Fig.2).

The bootstrap support increased for all clades when compared to the MP bootstrap values. The topology of the ML tree is identical to the consensus tree topology but with higher resolution.

The MP and ML analyses of the RPL16 clearly demonstrate that the *Juncus* species in Iraq are monophyletic genus. (Fig.1.2). in both analyses recovered this clades sister to the remaining species in the genus. the closed molecular character of the species *Juncus* obtained from RPL16 gene enhanced that these species has the same morphological feature of the *Juncus* genus in addition to distribution in the same geographic area.

Our investigation of *juncus* species revealed varied clade distributions for *Juncus* species in Iraq. This promotes the isolation and diversity of species from each other, whereas the convergence that occurs as a result of living in the same geographic region in Iraq and being impacted by the same condition as mentioned by (Al- Edhari et al., 2018) on his studied-on *Cephalaria* genotype in Iraq. Similar conclusion was observed by (Al-Badeiry, 2013) on her researching on the biodiversity of *Zea mays* varieties in Iraq.

Fig 1: Rpl16 Cladogram generated from parsimony bootstrap results are below branches .

Fig 2: Rpl16 Cladogram generated from neighbor joining bootstrap results are below branches ..

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